

Solution phase photocyclisation reaction of 2-hydroxychalcones to 4-flavanones

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Abstract : The photochemical cyclisation of 2-hydroxychalcones leading to the synthesis of 4-flavanones in solution phase has been investigated. The formation of photoproducts has been explained on the basis of excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) and the cyclisation efficiency of the chalcones has been found to depend upon the electron density on the phenolic oxygen as well as on the carbonyl group. This synthesis of flavanones by photoirradiation is an eco-friendly route with comparative yield to those of thermal methods. Although the molecular skeletons of these substrates is amenable to *cis-trans* isomerisations and cycloadditions but no photoproducts corresponding to these reactions have been realized.

Keywords : 2-Hydroxychalcone, flavanone, photoirradiation, H-transfer.

Introduction

Chalcones belong to a class of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds that form the central core for a variety of naturally occurring biologically active compounds with diverse pharmacological activities like antibacterial¹, antifungal², anti-tumor³ and anti-inflammatory⁴. The chalcones are also the important intermediates in the biosynthesis⁵ of flavanoids, the substances most abundantly found in plants. Substituted chalcones are of particular interest for the photochemical studies for their role as precursors in the biosynthesis of flavanoids⁶, their potential nonlinear optical properties⁷ and fluorescent probes for micellar solutions⁸. Photochemically, the chalcones are known to undergo photooxygenations⁹, photocycloadditions¹⁰⁻¹³ and *cis-trans* isomerisations¹⁴.

Additionally, there are few reports of excited state intramolecular proton transfers (ESIPT) in 2'-hydroxychalcone derivatives¹⁵⁻¹⁸. In some studies¹⁹, the chalcones underwent intramolecular hydrogen atom transfer through hydrogen bonding and tautomerisation to form flavanones. In the present study, we report the photoconversions of the substituted 2'-hydroxychalcones into the flavanones and also the effect of various substituents on the photochemical yield of flavanones.

Results and discussion

The target molecules i.e. the substituted chalcones 3(a-g) and 4(a-e) were synthesized by the condensation of a suitable acetophenone with a benzaldehyde using dry Ba(OH)₂ as base (Scheme 1). The physical and spectral

Scheme 1. Synthesis of chalcones 3(a-g) and 4(a-e).

data of the chalcones synthesized are listed in Table 1. In the 300 MHz, ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **3a**, the protons H-3', H-4' and H-6' were revealed at δ 6.99 (1H, d), 7.70 (1H, dd) and 7.88 (1H, d) respectively. The peak due to 2'-OH proton was a broad singlet at δ 12.73. The resonances due to H-2 and H-3 were present as doublets at δ 7.58 and 7.96 respectively, with J value of 15.3 Hz indicating *trans* stereochemistry at

C₂-C₃ double bond. The protons due to phenyl ring were placed as multiplet between δ 7.69–7.43. Similarly the ^1H NMR assignments of other chalcones **3(b-g)** and **4(a-e)** were found to be consistent with their structures (Table 1).

The deoxygenated solutions of the chalcones **3(a-g)** and **4(a-e)** (0.001 mol each) in dry benzene (100 ml) on irradiation with Pyrex filtered light from 125 W medium pressure mercury lamp (Scheme 2) for 8 h produced the

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of chalcones **3(a-g)** and **4(a-e)**

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C) (Lit. value)	IR (ν_{max}) (cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (δ) (300 MHz, CDCl_3)
3a	80	105–108 (108–109) ²⁰	1645.7 C=O str.	12.73 (s, 2'-OH), 7.96 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.88 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.70 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 7.58 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.49–7.43 (m, H-2'', 3'', 5'', 6''), 6.99 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 7.69 (m, H-4'')
3b	74	127–129 (131–133) ²⁰	1641.2	12.77 (br s, 2'-OH), 7.94 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.87 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.59 (d, J 8.1 Hz, H-3'', 5''), 7.58 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.44 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 7.26 (d, J 8.1 Hz, H-2'', 6''), 6.99 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 2.42 (s, 4''-CH ₃)
3c	89	100–102 (102–104) ²³	1638	12.85 (s, 2'-OH), 7.93 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.86 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.65 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3'', 5''), 7.28 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.42 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 6.98 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 6.96 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-2'', 6''), 3.87 (s, 4''-OCH ₃)
3d	90	151–153	1637.4	12.90 (s, 2'-OH), 7.88 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.87 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.46 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 7.43 (d, J 15.0 Hz, H-2), 6.99 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 6.90 (s, H-2'', 6''), 3.95 (s, 3'', 5''-OCH ₃), 3.93 (s, 4''-OCH ₃)
3e	81	166–168	1638.9	12.84 (s, 2'-OH), 12.14 (s, 4''-OH), 7.92 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.86 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.64 (d, J 8.4 Hz, H-2'', 6''), 7.45 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.44 (dd, J 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-4'), 6.99 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3'), 6.91 (d, J 8.4 Hz, H-3'', 5'')
3f	73	148–151 (149–150) ²⁴	1643.8	12.69 (s, 2'-OH), 7.88 (d, J 15.6 Hz, H-3), 7.86 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.63 (d, J 15.6 Hz, H-2), 7.45 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 7.32 (t, J 8.4 Hz, H-5''), 7.25 (d{t}, J 2.1, 8.4 Hz, H-6''), 7.16 (t, J 2.1 Hz, H-2''), 7.09 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 6.95 (d{t}, J 2.1, 8.1 Hz, H-4'')
3g	50	148–150	1628	12.76 (br s 2', 2''-OH), 8.13 (d, J 15.6 Hz, H-3), 7.81 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 7.72 (d, J 15.6 Hz, H-2), 7.54 (dd, J 2.1, 8.7 Hz, H-6''), 7.37 (dd, J 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-4'), 7.25 (d{t}, J 2.1, 8.7 Hz, H-4''), 6.98 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3'), 6.95 (d{t}, J 2.1, 8.7 Hz, H-5''), 6.79 (dd, J 2.1, 8.7 Hz, H-3'')
4a	78	84–85 (88–89) ²¹	1645.7	12.81 (s, 2'-OH), 7.94 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.93 (dd, J 1.8, 8.7 Hz, H-6'), 7.67 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.66 (m, H-2'', 6''), 7.54 (d{t}, J 1.8, 8.7 Hz, H-5'), 7.46–7.44 (m, H-3'', 4'', 5''), 7.04 (dd, J 1.8, 8.7 Hz, H-3'), 6.96 (d{t}, J 1.8, 8.1 Hz, H-4')
4b	72	183–184 (184–185) ²¹	1638	12.70 (s, 2'-OH), 7.92 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.69 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.63–7.58 (m, H-2'', 6''), 7.53 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.44–7.37 (m, H-3'', 4'', 5''), 7.39 (dd, J 1.5, 8.7 Hz, H-4'), 7.01 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3'), 2.48 (s, 5'-CH ₃)
4c	75	139–141 (142–144) ²²	1643	12.70 (s, 2'-OH), 7.93 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.86 (s, H-6'), 7.70–7.66 (m, H-2'', 6''), 7.56 (d, J 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.48–7.44 (m, H-3'', 4'', 5''), 6.93 (s, H-3'), 2.40 (s, 4'-CH ₃)
4d	67	106–107 (105) ²²	1637	12.81 (s, 2'-OH), 7.92 (d, J 15.0 Hz, H-3), 7.80 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-6'), 7.53–7.44 (m, H-2'', 6''), 7.47 (d, J 15.0 Hz, H-2), 6.54 (dd, J 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-5'), 6.49 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-3'), 3.88 (s, -OCH ₃)
4e	68	83–84	1634	12.59 (s, 2'-OH), 8.12 (d, J 8.4 Hz, H-8'), 7.92 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 7.91 (d, J 15.6 Hz, H-3), 7.85 (dd, J 1.5, 7.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.54 (d, J 15.6 Hz, H-2), 7.53 (d{t}, J 1.5, 8.4 Hz, H-7'), 7.45–7.32 (m, H-2'', 6'', 6'), 7.21 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3')

Note

Scheme 2. Photolysis of chalcones 3(a-g) and 4(a-e).

respective flavanones **5(a-g)** and **6(a-e)**. The structures of these photoproducts i.e. flavanones were ascertained from the physical and spectral data presented in Table 2. In ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **5a**, the resonances due to H-2, H_a -3 and H_b -3 protons were located at δ 5.48 (dd), 3.09 (dd) and 2.91 (dd) respectively.

The protons of two benzene rings resonated in the aromatic region between δ 7.02–7.89. The similar ^1H NMR patterns were displayed by the other photoproducts **5(b-g)** and **6(a-e)**. The ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) data of the flavanones **5(a-g)** and **6(a-e)** with δ values assigned to respective carbons is listed in Table 4.

Table 2. Physical and spectral data of flavanones **5(a-g)** and **6(a-e)**

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) (Lit. value)	IR (ν_{max}) (cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (δ) (300 MHz, CDCl_3)
5a R = 6-Cl R' = H	72	89–91 (90–93) ²⁰	1680 (C=O)	7.89 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.49–7.40 (m, H-7, H-2',6'), 7.02 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-8), 5.48 (dd, J 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 3.09 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.91 (1H, dd, J 16.8 Hz, H_a -3)
5b R = 6-Cl R' = 4'- CH_3	50	91–92 (93–94) ²⁷	1696	7.89 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.45 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.39 (d, J 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 7.26 (d, J 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.00 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-8), 5.45 (dd, J 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 3.10 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.91 (dd, J 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3), 2.38 (s, 4'- CH_3)
5c R = 6-Cl R' = 4'- OCH_3	60	97–99	1696	7.88 (d, J 2.7 Hz, H-5), 7.44 (dd, J 2.7, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.36 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3',5'), 6.98 (d, J 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 6.96 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-8), 5.42 (dd, J 2.7, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 3.83 (s, OCH_3), 3.10 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.89 (dd, J 2.7, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3)
5d R = 6-Cl R' = 3',4',5'- OCH_3	20	105–108	1698	7.89 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.46 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.04 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-8), 6.68 (s, H-2',6'), 5.39 (dd, J 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 3.89 (s, 3',5'- OCH_3), 3.87 (s, 4'- OCH_3), 3.08 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.92 (dd, J 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3)
5e R = 6-Cl R' = 4'-OH	18	180–182	1680	7.90 (d, J 2.7 Hz, H-5), 7.46 (dd, J 2.7, 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.37 (d, J 8.4 Hz, H-3',5'), 7.01 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-8), 6.91 (d, J 8.4 Hz, H-2',6'), 5.43 (dd, J 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 5.20 (br s, 4'-OH), 3.11 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.89 (dd, J 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3)
5f R = 6-Cl R' = 3'-OH	21	139–141	1681	7.90 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.47 (dd, J 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.32 (t, J 8.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.00 (d{t}, J 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-6'), 7.04 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-8), 6.99 (t, J 2.4 Hz, H-2'), 6.88 (d{t}, J 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-4'), 5.45 (dd, J 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 5.42 (br s, 3'-OH), 3.07 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.92 (dd, J 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3)
5g R = 6-Cl R' = 2'-OH	10	178–180	1695	7.84 (d, J 2.7 Hz, H-5), 7.39 (dd, J 2.7, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.31 (dd, J 2.4, 8.1 Hz, H-6'), 7.23 (m, J 2.4, 8.1 Hz, H-5'), 6.97 (d, J 9.0 Hz, H-8), 6.93 (t, J 8.1 Hz, H-4'), 6.82 (dd, J 2.4, 8.1 Hz, H-3'), 5.80 (br s, 3'-OH), 5.70 (dd, J 3.3, 13.6 Hz, H-2), 3.06 (dd, J 13.6, 17.1 Hz, H_b -3), 2.92 (dd, J 3.6, 17.1 Hz, H_a -3)
6a R' = H R = H	62	77–78 (76–78) ²⁵	1689	7.94 (dd, J 2.1, 7.8 Hz, H-5), 7.53 (d{dd} J 1.7, 7.1, 8.4 Hz, H-7), 7.10–7.05 (m, H-6,8), 7.49–7.35 (m, H-2'-6'), 5.65 (dd, J 3.0, 13.6 Hz, H-2), 3.06 (dd, J 13.6, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.86 (1H, dd, J 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3)
6b R' = H R = 6- CH_3	36	86–88	1695	7.73 (d, J 1.5 Hz, H-5), 7.51–7.38 (m, H-2'-6'), 7.33 (dd, J 1.5, 8.4 Hz, H-7), 6.96 (d, J 8.7 Hz, H-8), 5.46 (dd, J 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 3.08 (dd, J 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 2.88 (dd, J 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H_a -3), 2.33 (s, 6- CH_3)

6c R' = H R = 6-Cl; 7-CH ₃	48	85-87	1690	7.88 (d, <i>J</i> 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.48-7.37 (m, H-2',6'), 6.96 (s, H-8), 5.46 (dd, <i>J</i> 3.3, 12.9 Hz, H-2), 3.06 (dd, <i>J</i> 12.9, 16.8 Hz, H _b -3), 2.88 (dd, <i>J</i> 3.3, 16.8 Hz, H _a -3), 2.39 (s, 7-CH ₃)
6d R' = H R = 7-OCH ₃	40	85-86 (87-88) ²⁶	1680	7.90 (d, <i>J</i> 8.7 Hz, H-5), 7.52-7.40 (m, H-2'-6'), 6.64 (dd, <i>J</i> 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-6), 6.53 (d, <i>J</i> 2.4 Hz, H-8), 5.50 (dd, <i>J</i> 3.0, 13.2 Hz, H-2), 3.86 (s, -OCH ₃), 3.07 (dd, <i>J</i> 13.2, 16.8 Hz, H _b -3), 2.85 (dd, <i>J</i> 3.0, 16.8 Hz, H _a -3)
6e R' = H R = 5,6-benzo	30	102-104	1656	9.48 (d, <i>J</i> 8.7 Hz, H-5), 7.96 (d, <i>J</i> 9.0 Hz, H-9), 7.78 (d, <i>J</i> 8.1 Hz, H-8), 7.66 (d{t}, <i>J</i> 1.5, 8.7 Hz, H-6), 7.55-7.41 (m, H-2'-6',7), 7.19 (d, <i>J</i> 8.7 Hz, H-10), 5.61 (dd, <i>J</i> 3.0, 13.8 Hz, H-2), 3.23 (dd, <i>J</i> 13.8, 16.5 Hz, H _b -3), 2.99 (dd, <i>J</i> 3.0, 16.5 Hz, H _a -3)

Table 3. $\Delta H_f^\ddagger$ for the transition states of compound **3a** leading to the formation of 4-flavanone

State	I	II	III	IV	4-Flavanone
$\Delta H_f^\ddagger$ (kcal/mol)	-17.7805	-4.3830	7.8595	-11.1819	-20.6155

Table 4. ¹³C NMR data of photoproducts **5(a-g)** and **6(a-e)**

Compd.	¹³ C NMR (δ) (75.5 MHz, CDCl ₃)
5a	190.81 (C-4), 159.96 (C-8a), 138.24 (C-1'), 136.03 (C-7), 128.96 (C-3', C-5'), 128.91 (C-2', C-6'), 127.20 (C-4'), 126.39 (C-5), 126.14 (C-6), 121.71 (C-4a), 119.68 (C-8), 79.82 (C-2), 44.27 (C-3)
5b	206.88 (C-4), 159.10 (C-8a), 139.00 (C-4'), 135.96 (C-7), 135.10 (C-1'), 129.54 (C-3', C-5'), 126.90 (C-6), 126.36 (C-5), 126.18 (C-2', C-6'), 122.00 (C-4a), 119.88 (C-8), 79.74 (C-2), 44.14 (C-3), 30.88 (4'-CH ₃)
5c	191.05 (C-4), 160.11 (C-4'), 160.03 (C-8a), 135.96 (C-7), 130.26 (C-1'), 127.73 (C-2', C-6'), 127.09 (C-6), 126.36 (C-5), 121.69 (C-4a), 119.87 (C-8), 114.26 (C-3', C-5'), 79.57 (C-2), 55.36 (4'-OCH ₃), 44.04 (C-3)
5d	189.21 (C-4), 160.04 (C-8a), 153.20 (C-3', C-5'), 141.26 (C-4'), 136.18 (C-7), 131.70 (C-1'), 127.11 (C-6), 126.12 (C-5), 121.40 (C-4a), 119.77 (C-8), 102.76 (C-2', C-6'), 79.37 (C-2), 56.85 (3',5'-OCH ₃), 56.30 (4'-OCH ₃), 43.90 (C-3)
5e	191.18 (C-4), 160.04 (C-8a), 156.22 (C-4'), 136.03 (C-7), 130.41 (C-1'), 127.96 (C-2', C-6'), 127.13 (C-6), 126.37 (C-5), 121.66 (C-4a), 119.87 (C-8), 115.71 (C-3', C-5'), 79.52 (C-2), 44.05 (C-3)
5f	190.79 (C-4), 159.86 (C-8a), 156.10 (C-3'), 140.07 (C-1'), 136.07 (C-7), 130.20 (C-5'), 127.26 (C-6), 126.39 (C-5), 121.70 (C-4a), 119.86 (C-8), 118.33 (C-6'), 115.87 (C-4'), 113.08 (C-2'), 79.43 (C-2), 44.23 (C-3)
5g	189.72 (C-4), 158.23 (C-8a), 151.79 (C-2'), 134.55 (C-7), 128.54 (C-6'), 126.15 (C-1'), 125.46 (C-4'), 125.12 (C-5), 122.84 (C-6), 120.47 (C-4a), 119.61 (C-8), 118.37 (C-5'), 115.04 (C-3'), 75.05 (C-2), 41.33 (C-3)
6a	191.42 (C-4), 151.53 (C-8a), 138.36 (C-1'), 136.18 (C-7), 128.84 (C-3',5'), 128.81 (C-2',6'), 127.49 (C-6), 127.34 (C-4'), 127.17 (C-5), 121.50 (C-4a), 118.17 (C-8), 78.51 (C-2), 44.11 (C-3)
6b	190.82 (C-4), 158.15 (C-8a), 139.27 (C-1'), 137.28 (C-7), 131.05 (C-6), 128.83 (C-3',5'), 128.36 (C-5), 126.62 (C-4'), 126.15 (C-2',6'), 121.22 (C-4a), 117.92 (C-8), 79.58 (C-2), 44.73 (C-3), 20.04 (6-ClH ₃)
6c	190.65 (C-4), 159.04 (C-8a), 142.70 (C-7), 141.26 (C-1'), 128.86 (C-3',5'), 127.21 (C-2',6'), 126.73 (C-4'), 126.72 (C-5), 126.11 (C-6), 121.40 (C-4a), 120.19 (C-8), 79.75 (C-2), 44.28 (C-3), 20.84 (7-CH ₃)
6d	185.90 (C-4), 166.80 (C-7), 162.24 (C-8a), 140.51 (C-1'), 128.85 (C-5), 128.78 (C-3', C-5'), 127.20 (C-4'), 126.16 (C-2', C-6'), 118.21 (C-4a), 110.27 (C-6), 100.95 (C-8), 79.93 (C-2), 55.65 (7-OCH ₃), 44.35 (C-3)
6e	192.98 (C-4), 163.70 (C-10a), 138.53 (C-1'), 137.59 (C-9), 131.47 (C-4b), 129.70 (C-8a), 129.29 (C-6), 128.86 (C-3', C-5'), 128.81 (C-2', C-6'), 128.38 (C-4'), 126.17 (C-8), 125.90 (C-5), 124.93 (C-7), 118.85 (C-10), 112.61 (C-4a), 79.62 (C-2), 45.73 (C-3)

In the ground state structure of the acrylophenone (**3a**), the strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the phenolic proton and the carbonyl oxygen leads to a six-membered cyclic T.S. (**I**) that is supported well by the PMR spectra ($\delta_{\text{OH}} \sim 12.7$). The photoconversion of the chalcone to the flavanone can be envisioned to occur through the excited state intramolecular proton transfer

(ESIPT) through the $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ excited state in a configuration similar to *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde type of ESIPT²⁸. In the $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ excited state, phenolic group usually becomes more acidic and carbonyl more basic, enhancing proton transfer²⁹ to give the enol (**II**) in *trans*-configuration (Scheme 3). The tautomer *trans*-**II** undergoes a conformational rotation into the form **III** followed by a thermal

Scheme 3. Mechanism of formation of flavanone

6π -electrocyclic ring-closure to give **IV** which subsequently undergoes tautomerisation to yield 4-flavanone. The cyclisation of **III** to **IV** may be exothermic or less endothermic due to the restoration of aromatic sextet of the phenyl ring ensuring the stability and proceeds effectively via a thermal 6π -electrocyclic process. Padwa *et al.*³⁰ have shown that the photochemical rearrangement of 3-chromanone derivatives takes place via enolisation and a similar mechanism has been proposed for the photochemical ring opening reaction of substituted 4-flavanones³¹.

In compound **3a**, the calculation of heat of formation ($\Delta H_f^\ddagger$) by MOPAC-PM3 program for the transition states **I-IV** and the 4-flavanone is shown in Table 3.

A closer look at Table 3 shows the conversion of **I**→**II**→**III** is an endothermic process and thus requires the photochemical energy. The conversions **III**→**IV**→4-flavanone are exothermic and can proceed well with the dissipation of energy.

The effect of substituents present at benzoyl moiety and styrenyl moiety of chalcone molecule on the photochemical yield of flavanone is shown in Table 2.

As shown in Scheme 3 in the conversion of these chalcones into flavanones, the first step is the transfer of phenolic proton to the carbonyl group to form enol-II. The ease of hydrogen transfer is related to the type and energy of excited state of carbonyl involved and the acidity of the phenolic proton. This reaction is similar to intramolecular photo-reduction. The groups that exert elec-

tron-donating effect (Ring A) on the phenolic oxygen lower the acidity of phenolic proton and make its transfer to carbonyl less facile. On the other hand, the electron donating groups also lower the energy of π - π^* excited state of the carbonyl chromophore as compared to n - π^* state which also make the proton transfer less efficient. It is evident from the Table 2, that as the electron density is increased on the carbonyl chromophore (in case of compounds **4d**, R = 4'-OCH₃ and **4c**, 4'-CH₃) or phenolic oxygen (in case of compounds **4b**, R = 5'-CH₃ and **4e**, 5',6'-benzo) the cyclisation efficiency decreases and the yield of flavanone is lowered. A similar effect is perceived from the Table 2 that as electron density increases on styrenyl moiety (R' = H→CH₃→OCH₃→OH) the proton transfer becomes less efficient and cyclisation efficiency decreases.

Conclusion :

It may be concluded that the photoirradiation of substituted 2'-hydroxychalcones produced 4-flavanones and the cyclisation efficiency depends upon the electron density on phenolic oxygen as well as on the carbonyl group. This photochemical synthesis of flavanones is an eco-friendly route with comparative yield to those of thermal methods. Although the molecular skeletons of these substrates is amenable to *cis-trans* isomerisations and cycloadditions but no photoproducts corresponding to these reactions were realized.

Experimental

General :

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are thus uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on a Buck Scientific 500 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. TLC plates were coated with silica gel G (suspended in CHCl₃-MeOH) and iodine vapours were used as visualizing agent. The columns for purification were packed with silica gel 100–200 mesh in petroleum ether (60–80 °C)-benzene (9 : 1) and left overnight before use. The elution was carried out with increasing proportion of benzene in petroleum ether-benzene mixture. To maintain inert atmosphere during photolysis 99.9% dry N₂ gas was continuously bubbled through the reaction solution.

Synthesis of chalcones 3(a-g) and 4(a-e) :

General procedure : A solution of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol and dehydrated S200 barium hydroxide (0.02 mol) was refluxed on water bath for 20 min. The solution was cooled and poured onto crushed ice; it was then acidified with conc. HCl to give a yellow solid. The solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol to give the yellow product **3a**.

The other 2-hydroxychalcones **3(b-g)** and **4(a-e)** were synthesized by reacting substituted 2-hydroxyacetophenone **1** with variously substituted benzaldehyde **2** under the reaction conditions as used for compound **3a**.

Photolysis of chalcones 3(a-g) and 4(a-e) :

General procedure : A deoxygenated solution of the chalcone **3a** (0.001 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was irradiated with Pyrex filtered light from 125 W medium pressure mercury lamp for 8 h. The color of the solution became yellow. Solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and a gummy mass was obtained which was then chromatographed over silica-gel (100–200 mesh) using benzene-petroleum ether as an eluent. Elution of the column gave the starting chalcone (13%, co-tlc and mmp) and the photoproduct **9** (78%).

The other substrates **3(b-g)** and **4(a-e)** (0.001 mol each) were photolysed under the similar conditions in their benzene solution.

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References

1. R. Li, G. L. Kenyon, F. E. Cohen, X. Chen, B. Gong, J. N. Dominquez, E. Davidson, G. Kurzban, R. E. Miller and E. O. Nuzum, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 5031.
2. P. Boeck, P. C. Leal, R. A. Yunes, V. C. Filho, S. López, M. Sortino, A. Escalante, R. L. E. Furlán and S. Zacchin. *J. Archiv der Parmarie*, 2005, **338**, 85.
3. Y. Xia, Z. Yang, P. Xia, K. F. Bastow, Y. Nakanishi and K. Lee, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2000, **10**, 699.
4. Y. H. Kim, J. Kim, H. Park and H. P. Kim, *Biol. Pharm. Bull.*, 2007, **30**, 1450.
5. (a) L. Jurd, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 987; (b) *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 2394; (c) *Tetrahedron*, 1969, **25**, 2367.
6. D. N. Dhar, "The Chemistry of Chalcones and Related Compounds", John Wiley and Sons, Inc, New York, 1981.
7. P. Wang and S. Wu, *J. Luminescence*, 1994, **62**, 33.
8. Y. B. Jiang, X. J. Wang and L. Lin, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1994, **98**, 2368.
9. T. L. Brack, S. Conti, C. Rodu and N. W. Jurcsak, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 3995.
10. S. Kar and S. Lahiri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2000, **40**, 1121.
11. F. R. Cibin, G. Doddi and P. Mencarelli, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 3455.
12. F. R. Cibin, N. D. Bello, G. Doddi, B. Fares, P. Mencarelli and E. Ullucci, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 9971.
13. N. Yayli, O. Ucuncu, E. Aydin, Y. Gok, A. Yasar, C. Baltaci, N. Yildirim and M. Kuruk, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2005, **169**, 229.
14. (a) R. Matsushima, S. Fuzimoto and K. Tokumura, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2001, **74**, 827; (b) D. Song, K. Jung, J. Moon and D. Shin, *Optical Materials*, 2003, **21**, 1.
15. H. Horiuchi, H. Shirase, T. Okutsu, R. Matsushima and H. Hiratsuka, *Chem. Lett.*, 2000, **29**, 96.
16. R. Matsushima, H. Mizuno and A. Kaziura, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1994, **67**, 1762.
17. R. Matsushima and M. Suzuki, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **65**, 39.
18. R. Matsushima, K. Kato and S. Ishigar, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2002, **75**, 2079.
19. (a) T. Arai and Y. Norikane, *Chem. Lett.*, 1997, 339; (b) R. Matsushima and H. Kageyama, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 743.

Note

20. J. F. Batchelor, D. J. Bauer, H. F. Hodson, J. W. T. Selway and D. A. B. Young, US Patent 4461907, 1984.
21. (a) K. V. Auwers *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1932, **218**, 493; (b) Y. Hoshino, T. Oohinata and N. Takeno, *Nippon Kagaku kaishi*, 1985, 2104; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1986, **59**, 2351.
22. Y. Ohkatsu and T. Satoh, *Journal of the Japan Petroleum Institute*, 2008, **51**, 298.
23. N. De Meyer, A. Haemers, L. Mishra, H. K. Pandey, L. A. Pieters, D. A. V. Berghe and A. J. Vlietinck, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 736.
24. S. H. Jung, S. Y. Park, Y. K. Pak, H. K. Lee, K. S. Park, K. H. Shin, K. Ohuchi, H. K. Shin, S. R. Keum and S. S. Lim, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2006, **54**, 368.
25. Y. Ohkatsu and T. Satoh, *Journal of the Japan Petroleum Institute*, 2008, **51**, 298.
26. (a) J. J. P. Furlong *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 633; (b) Bani Talapatra Tulika Deb and Sunil Talapatra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*. 1986, **25**, 1122.
27. G. F. Katekar and A. G. Moritz, *Australian J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 2337.
28. A. Nagaoka and U. Nagashima, *Chem. Phys.*, 1989, **136**, 153.
29. (a) S. Greth, O. Levy, M. Markovits and A. Shaw, *Tetrahedron*, 1975, **31**, 2803; (b) A. Weller, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1950, **60**, 1144; (c) J. Goodman and L. E. Brus, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 7472; (d) R. Rossetti, R. C. Haddon and L. E. Brus, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 6913; (e) H. D. Becker, "The Chemistry of Hydroxyl Group", ed. S. Patai, John Wiley and Sons, Inc, London, Part II, 1971, pp. 894-920.
30. A. Padwa, A. Au, G. A. Lee and W. Owens, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 3555.
31. R. Nakashima, K. Okamoto and T. Matsuura, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1976, **49**, 3355.

